

**THE ISLAMISM OF SOCIAL RESEARCH, AND USE OF THE MODERN
TECHNOLOGICAL MEDIA**

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ABSTRACT

Islamization of human sciences is a widely discussed topic in Islamic intellectual discourse since it does not work in opposition to modern science, but rather as an ally of it. Efforts are being undertaken to incorporate Islamic knowledge into current human/social science in order to promote Islamization. By assessing needs, prospects, and obstacles, Muslim social scientists have made major contributions to the field of human understanding Islamization, according to this study. According to a review of relevant literature, in order to develop and preserve Islamic Civilization, modern civilization must embrace Islamize human sciences. Many attempts have been made by Islamic sociologists from all around the Muslim world to introduce and incorporate Islamization into societies. These educational institutions, which have been established and curricula and courses implemented, are teaching Islamization of human sciences. Islamic sociology is one of the endeavours in the quest to comprehend society's faults from an Islamic perspective and how to address them in light of the Quran and Sunnah. Despite the excellent achievements of Muslim social scientists, several hurdles exist. Inadequate training and instruction to integrate Islamic philosophy into the curriculum are among them. Progress is hampered by issues in sociology, politics, economics, and religion. To advance Islamization of Human Sciences today, the Muslim Ummah should unite under an unified worldview and ideology.

Keywords: Mulim, Islamic, Social Sciences, Intellectual, , Ummah

INTRODUCTION

Its Islamization of Human Knowledge examines Islam and modern science in the context of today's intellectual debate. In the last decade, a number of attempts have been made to put the notion of Islamizing Knowledge into practise, including the publication of books and text

materials, as well as the establishment of institutions that provide similar academic programmes. Two of the most renowned scholars involved in the project's early stages were Syed Muhammad Naquibal Attas and the late Isma'ilRaji al-Faruqi. Both of them endeavoured to define and explain the problem as well as the theory through their writings.

Before digging into a specific topic, it is necessary to understand the principles of Islamization, Islamization of Knowledge, and their application in Human Sciences, specifically Islamic Sociology.

Islamization is a process of converting a culture to Islam by imparting a strong sense of faith, conviction in Islamic values, and putting those beliefs into practise on a personal and communal level. In the modern realm of human sciences, Islamization can be defined as the process of obtaining an education based on Islamic objectives and techniques and then altering it to benefit the entire society at a later date. As a result, Islamization is also known as "da'wah," and it was the Prophet Muhammad's S.A.W. goal to do this (Abdallah, 2013). To put it another way, when we talk about the Islamization of Knowledge, we're talking about Islamization in general. The theory's proponents claim that Malaysian scholar Syed Muhammad Naqib al Attas is the brains behind it.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To determine whether or not humanities should be islamized in Muslim countries
2. Explore the current state of Islamization as it pertains to humanities and communication by looking at current trends.

METHODOLOGY

There is no way to identify or symbolically express a single scientific technique. Every systematic technique, including the scientific method, is founded on a set of fundamentals. The scientific method includes measuring and gathering data through observation and experimentation, as well as forming hypotheses, according to Merriam-definition: Webster's Webster's principles and processes for the systematic pursuit of knowledge. When these principles are taken into account, the researcher can declare the study or outcome to be scientific. The scientific method, on the other hand, is not confined to the aforementioned criterion; rather, a new approach can be justified if it is sound. The study is conceptualised using secondary data

from books and academic papers. Muslim social scientists such as Al-Faruqi, Al-shariati, Jamil Farooqui, Abraham Ragab, and Abu Suylaman investigated Islamization of Human Sciences in depth. The researchers used previously published work by several authors as a point of reference.

NEED FOR ISLAMIZATION

Because of the history of knowledge transformation brought about by Islamization, Islamization in social sciences is required. It can be traced back to the establishment of an Islamic society based on Islamic and Quranic ideals of living throughout the time period of Islamic civilization. Islamic civilization's main purpose was to promote Islam's foundational ideals of peace and fairness in society. Muslim philosophers from antiquity offered their knowledge and abilities to the formulation of Quranic epistemological concepts required to reorganise Muslim civilizations in order to construct a well-built ummah (community) (Choudhury, 1999).

Islam's golden age began to come to an end when western culture arrived in the 15th century. Western scholars began to create their own intellectual foundations by incorporating Muslim scholars' knowledge and contributions from various Muslim organisations, resulting in a lack of desire for Muslim scholars to seek knowledge. After the 18th century, a number of countries, notably Turkey, Persia, Iran, and India, launched contemporary Islamic initiatives to bring Muslims together in order to save the Ummah and Islamic knowledge (Barzinji, 1999). During that time period, the Muslim Ummah's deteriorating image did not improve since the ideology they adopted did not focus on the actual crisis, and the movements did not represent all of the Muslim Ummah's concerns. After other youth movements began to build tangible techniques of infusing Islamic knowledge into western discourse, the International Institute of Islamic Thought (IIIT) was founded in the United States of America in 1981. Since then, a number of conferences have been conducted across the Muslim world to examine the Islamization of knowledge and to investigate various approaches for introducing Islamization into the human sciences. The institute started working on the Islamization of knowledge right away (Ahsan, et al, 2013).

NEED FOR ISLAMIZATION OF COMMUNICATION knowledge

The Islamicization of Knowledge's main focus points

- Engage in Islamic knowledge-based activities (discovery, collection composition and publication).
- To incorporate all human endeavours and sciences, both theoretical and applied, within an Islamic framework.
- to make sure that Islam's capacity to think, think, think is compatible with the needs and challenges of the Ummah (Muslim nation).

Generally In the early twentieth century, when Muslim countries gained independence from colonial domination, they were encouraged to revitalise Islamic philosophy and integrate it into the modern realm of human sciences. As a result of Muslim philosophers' continued fight in the late twentieth century, scientific research ideas have aligned with Islamic Social Sciences. Muslims and non-Muslims alike are interested in research on the Islamization of scientific knowledge (Nadvi, 2013).

Al-FaruqI goes on to outline a twelve-step process for achieving the work plan's objectives and the Islamization of modern knowledge. Mastering of modern professions, disciplinary study, mastery of the Islamic history and present, establishment of Islam's basic importance to disciplines, critical review and appraisal of the state-of-the-art at each step are all required. The latest modern scientific and technological advancements, Creative analyses and Ummah's major challenges are analysed and synthesised. Discipline rewriting in the Islamic tradition: university textbooks; Islamic knowledge distribution. These safeguards ensure that Muslims growing up in the West are aware of and are capable of mastering the disciplines (Hashim, 2000). As it has progressed to a more defined destination, adherence and acceptability have increased. He highlighted two routes for promoting IOK: Islamization of social science and reforms in Islamic sciences.

Al-Attas' process of Islamization of contemporary knowledge has two stages:

Western ideas and concepts are excluded from the remainder of what is previously known about Islamic concepts and elements combined in it.

Knowledge must be imbued with Islamic elements and key concepts after being separated from each branch by foreign elements and key concepts, he claims.

While progress has been made, there is more work to be done in order to make the approach or work plan universally applicable to Muslim contributors. Furthermore, Muslim intellectuals in

both Muslim and non-Muslim countries have devised a number of tactics and programmes to promote the Islamization of human sciences. The International Islamic Conference, on the other hand.

These educational institutions aim to return the Muslim Ummah's dynamic and progressive role in all sectors of knowledge and intellectual discussion to that of educational excellence. The goal to disseminate Islamic-oriented knowledge and research in a way that supports Muslim unity and justice is the driving force behind the establishment of Islamic centres and universities. In university curricula, it is critical to emphasise knowledge-based activities (such as research, seminars, and conferences) while keeping an Islamic worldview in mind.

The Islamic universities' general principles for promoting the Islamization of human sciences are as follows:

- Relationship between human sciences and Quranic or Islamic viewpoints.
- To improve one's ability to analyse and evaluate modern social science theories, methods and systems, develop critical thinking skills. Restructure them in accordance with Islamic principles
- Compare different disciplines to identify Islamic perspectives' positive characteristics.
- The explanation of Islamic ideas and theories, as well as Islamic values, conventions, and schools of thought, in current curricula.

CONCLUSION

In the Islamization of knowledge, which is required by today's worldwide Muslim population around the world, contemporary social sciences are blended with revealed knowledge. The research addressed various approaches for integrating Islamization of knowledge into current sciences. Islamization of human sciences begins with the introduction of Islamic perspectives into all current scientific fields through the development of ties and connections between them. Islamic sociology is a branch of the Human Sciences that aims to investigate society and its issues from an Islamic perspective, rather than as a rejection of current science but as a complement to it.

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